

Logarithm of Quantum Wavefunction as a Partition Function

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In quantum mechanics, one focuses on densities such as the probability density $W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, and expectation values $W^*(x)$ Operator $W(x)$ (integrated over space). The question then is what is the significance of the wavefunction $W(x)$? In this note, we argue that $\ln(W(x))$ can act as a partition function with the added probability factor $\sin(px)$ multiplied by $f(p)$ in a Fourier expansion of $W(x)$. The factor $\sin(px)$ contains both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ and so represents both forward and backward motion which are usually separated in time and which accounts for a wavelength. This approach allows one to calculate an average kinetic energy which satisfies: $KE + V(x) = E$ where $V(x)$ is the potential at any point x and E the energy. It is possible that this approach has appeared before in the literature, but we are unaware of any specific paper. We consider the case in which $f(p) = \sin(px) \exp(-p^2/a)$ where a is a constant and show that it is associated with a harmonic oscillator.

Partition function

In classical statistical mechanics, one can write a partition function as:

$$-kT \ln \left\{ \sum \exp(-p^2/2mT) \right\}$$

This suggests that the probability to find a particle with momentum p is $\exp(-p^2/2mT) / \ln \left\{ \sum \exp(-p^2/2mT) \right\}$

If a potential is present, $p^2/2m$ is replaced with $+ V(r)$, where $V(r)$ is the potential.

It seems the quantum wavefunction $W(x)$ (in one dimension here) is closely related to this idea of a partition function. The difference seems to be that for each momentum p , there is an associated spatial probability which takes the form of $\sin(px)$. This may be related to zitterbewegung as the particle seems to have motion in a region the size of the wavelength. The specific choice of $\sin(px)$ to represent this "probability" of position, however, also seems to be related to wave motion. The 2x2 matrix model [1] also predicts a particle that moves back and forth with zitterbewegung while moving along with an average speed of v . It should also be noted that $\sin(px)$ contains $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ representing forward and backward motion. With this "spatial probability" a partition function can be written as proportional to:

$\ln \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \left[\sin(px) f(p) \right] \right\}$ (1) where $f(p)$ is a probability related to momentum p .

And the probability to have a particular p as:

$$f(p) \sin(px) / \ln \left\{ \sum \text{over } p \left[\sin(px) f(p) \right] \right\}$$

This is interesting because depending on the point x chosen, $\sin(px)$ alters the overall probability $\sin(px) f(p)$ unlike the classical case where the probability is simply $f(p)$. We note that $\sin(px)$ contains $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ which we argue represent zitterbewegung particles moving to the right and left. Thus, $\sin(px)$ is already incorporating an average of these two motions which would usually occur at very different times. It seems that this average is in place whether E is low and time resolution is low or E is high and time resolution is high due to the E-t uncertainty principle.

The average kinetic energy can then be calculated from the partition function (1) as:

$$\text{Sum } p^2/2m \sin(px) f(p) / \text{Sum}\{ f(p) \sin(px)\} \quad (2)$$

The denominator is the wavefunction acting as a normalization constant which is actually a function of x . It should be noted that the average kinetic energy at a point x (not the kinetic energy density) is calculated strictly using the idea of a wavefunction. There is no notion of $W^*(x)W(x)$ in this calculation.

Now, if one imposes conservation of energy for this average kinetic energy, namely:

$$\text{KE ave} + V(x) = E$$

then one obtains the time independent Schrodinger equation.

$$\text{Sum } \{p^2/2m \sin(px) f(p)\} / \text{Sum}\{ f(p) \sin(px)\} + V(x) = E \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Or } (\hbar)^2 1/2m \text{del}^2 W(x) + V(x)W(x) = EW(x)$$

The differential equation form is interesting because mathematically, the energy operator $(\hbar)^2 1/2m \text{del}^2 + V(x)$ acting on $W(x)$ should not change the distribution as one has a time independent solution. Thus, there needs to be solutions to this eigenvalue differential equation which is of a Sturm-Liouville type and should have discrete eigenvalues. (One can specify $W(x)=0$ at infinity.)[2] It is even more interesting because these eigenvalues E are discrete, not continuous. A first glance at (3) might suggest the possibility of any value of E as in classical physics, but this is not the case.

A further issue is the connection of the time independent Schrodinger equation, presented here as a type of statistical equation and the time dependent case. From time dependent theory there should be a time factor of $\exp(iEt)$ implying periodic motion. What does this periodic motion represent here? From the uncertainty principle for E and t , high E seems to imply high energy resolution and vice versa. Thus, the periodicity of $\exp(iEt)$ may represent the period of time during which one cannot really resolve time. This might explain the need for a statistical approach, i.e. $\ln(W(x))$ including all possible momenta even forward and backward motion.

There may, however, be a physical oscillation related to the energy acting among the probability for p .

Harmonic Oscillator

As a specific example, consider assigning $f(p) = \exp(-p^2/a)$ where a is a constant. This is the probability from classical statistical mechanics. This leads to a partition function with a Gaussian wavefunction which is the ground state for $V(x) = bx^2$. It is interesting that this connection with statistical mechanics only exists for the oscillator potential. The quantum mechanical partition function $\ln(W(x))$ is associated with a Gaussian wavefunction which matches the form of the classical statistical mechanical density. This Gaussian wavefunction only holds for the ground state energy. It should be noted that in statistical mechanics, one has $+p$ and $-p$ particles in a each small box centered at x and that these create a physical pressure. For the quantum mechanical wavefunction $W(x)$ one also has $+p$ and $-p$ (forming $\sin(px)$), but it is not clear that these represent any kind of pressure, but only a statistical averaging.

For higher energies, it is as if quantized oscillations are being added to the oscillator system as the energy increases by $\hbar \omega n$ where n is an integer and ω the angular frequency. This changes $f(p)$ from $\exp(-p^2/a)$ to a result which yields $W(x) = \exp(-x^2/b) H_n(x)$ where $H_n(x)$ is a Hermite polynomial, but the conservation of energy still applies at each point x with the average kinetic energy being used and the factor $\sin(px)$ still applies to $f(p)$ as this appears to be a property of particle (related to zitterbewegung).

Classical Case: Is there a relationship with the Schrodinger Equation?

The spatial density of the quantum mechanical oscillator ground state and classical statistical mechanical result are of the same form. As noted, however, statistical mechanics contains a physical pressure in a box at point x with particles moving to the right and left. In quantum mechanics, $W(x)$ also has $+p$ and $-p$, but it is not clear that these are related to pressure. The kinetic energy is also different as the quantum case (2) is position dependent and includes $\sin(px)$ in the formula which can suppress some $p^2/2m$ terms compared to others.. One may ask, however, if this quantum mechanical scenario could possibly describe a classical case. It seems that if there are waves (e.g. sound) associated with the momenta (with the form $\sin(px)$), then $\exp(-p^2/2mT) \sin(px)$ could have meaning even a classical case and would lead to a classical statistical mechanical harmonic oscillator density.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it appears that the time independent Schrodinger equation may be obtained using $\ln(W(x))$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, as a partition function. This partition function can be written as $\ln \{ \text{Sum over } p [\sin(px) f(p)] \}$ where $\sin(px)$ includes $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ or forward and backward motion which are normally separated in time. The partition function leads

to classical conservation of energy: $KE_{ave} + V(x) = E$ which in turn leads to the Schrodinger equation. This can be written as a differential equation in $W(x)$ which is of Sturm Liouville form and allows for discrete eigenvalues namely E . With $f(p)=\exp(-ap^2)$, a result from statistical mechanics, one obtains the harmonic oscillator ground state wavefunction. It is suggested that perhaps this partition function approach to quantum mechanics could be applied to classical statistical mechanics if physical circumstance (such as perhaps sound waves) would allow for $\sin(px)$ being included with $\exp(-ap^2)$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco. 2x2 Matrix Method and the Schrodinger Equation. (Zenodo, 2018)
2. Ruel Churchill, James Ward Brown. Fourier Series and Boundary Value Problems.(McGraw Hill, 1987)